

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Poland.....	3
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Poland: An Introduction	12
2.2. <i>The Provision of Local Public Transport</i>	15
2.3. <i>Provision of Internet Infrastructure by Local Government: A Step Towards Smart Villages</i>	18
2.4. <i>Lack of Effective Housing Management in Communes and Attempts to Recover from the Crisis</i> ...	25
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Poland: An Introduction	32
3.2. <i>Investment Expenditure of Local Governments: The Role of European Funds in the Financial Strategies of Rural gminas</i>	42
3.3. <i>Integrated Territorial Investment (ITI)</i>	46
3.4. <i>The Importance of the ‘Village Fund’ for the Mobilization of Rural Residents to Civic Participation</i>	50
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Poland: An Introduction	56
4.2. <i>What does Metropolitan Cooperation in the Functional Area of the Capital Warsaw Involve?</i>	62
4.3. <i>First Territorial Unit of Metropolitan Nature in Poland: The Metropolitan Union ‘Upper Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis’</i>	67
4.4. <i>The Association ‘Gdansk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area’ as an Example of Urban–Rural Cooperation</i>	75
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction.....	83
5.2. <i>Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government</i>	85
5.3. <i>County-Commune Unions as a New Form of Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Beskidian County and Commune Union</i>	88
5.4. <i>The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations</i>	94
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Poland: An Introduction	102
6.2. <i>Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expense of the Rural Area: Consultations with Residents or a Local Referendum?</i>	106
6.3. <i>Youth Commune Council in Poland</i>	115
6.4. <i>Participatory Fund in Cities</i>	120

Local Financial Arrangements

3.4. The Importance of the ‘Village Fund’ for the Mobilization of Rural Residents to Civic Participation

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Relevance of the Practice

The practice of participatory budget initiated in Porto Alegre is widely known in the world. The democratic discussion and decision-making process was developed primarily in municipalities. In Poland, the participatory budget occurs in cities.⁸³ Yet, there is also a similar instrument in rural areas.

The fundamental difference is that the participatory budget for rural areas was introduced by virtue of the Act of 21 February 2014 on the ‘Village fund’, which regulates its functioning in a uniform manner throughout Poland.

The differences between the participatory budgeting procedure and the ‘Village fund’:

First, the participatory budget was created as an informal bottom-up initiative of city residents. Local governments of particular cities decided to conduct it in order to present themselves as friendly to residents and open to their needs. There was no top-down regulation in the form of a central parliamentary act. Each city decided on its own about introducing a participatory budget and the procedure form.

There was a difference with ‘Village fund’ as it was established by a central parliamentary act, which introduced the same procedure for all local governments in Poland. However, the decision concerning the village council fund establishment in a given commune is voluntary - it is passed by the commune council.

Second, the participatory budget in cities is financed only from the local government's own funds. The different situation occurs in the case of the ‘Village fund’. The part of the financial resources comes from the communes’ budgets, while some funds are transferred from the central (state) budget.

Contrary to the idea that the participatory budget is not regulated from the top-down by a law, the central parliament passed an act in 2018 stating that the creation of a participatory budget is obligatory in cities with county rights. The act also regulates the participatory budget procedure and the minimum amount of funds allocated from the city budget to the participatory budget.

⁸³ See report section 6.4. on the Participatory Fund in Cities.

The ‘Village fund’ means the financial resources which can be separated from the budget of the rural communes and the urban-rural communes and guaranteed for the *sołectwo*⁸⁴ (an auxiliary unit of a rural or urban-rural *gmina*) in order to carry out projects falling within the category of the *gmina*’s own tasks, aimed at improving living conditions of residents of rural areas. From the point of view of rural residents, it is an instrument of budgetary participation, i.e. co-decision on expenditures of determined parts of public resources included in the municipality budget and aimed at supporting grassroots initiatives of rural residents.

‘The Village fund’ may be interpreted as:

- a democratic discussion and decision-making process by rural community;
- an element of financial management of rural and urban–rural *gminas*;
- an instrument of direct task accomplishment by rural residents.

Gminas that separate financial resources from their budget in order to establish the ‘Village fund’ receive a financial bonus from the Polish government budget which amounts to 20 per cent, 30 per cent or 40 per cent of the expenditure made by *sołectwos*. The bonus amount depends on the wealth of *gmina*. *Gminas* with the *lowest income* receive the *highest subsidies*.

Description of the Practice

The ‘Village fund’ implemented according to the act requires compliance with procedures and time limits. However, the entire process is not complicated.

The establishment of the fund is the right of the *gmina* council, the resolution on granting the consent to separate the fund applies to the subsequent budgetary years, however, the resolution on not granting the consent to separate it applies only to the budgetary year following the year in which the resolution was adopted.

Therefore, the first step is the ‘Village fund’ establishment decided by the *gmina* council in a particular rural or urban-rural *gmina*. The amount of the resources assigned to the given *sołectwo* is calculated on the basis of a formula determined in the act where the wealth of the municipality and the number of the village residents are the primary variables.

The second step is the decision of the *sołectwo* to benefit from the financial resources of the ‘Village fund’. The condition for granting the resources from the fund in the given budgetary year is that a request is submitted by the given *sołectwo* to the executive body (to the mayor).

⁸⁴ A *sołectwo* is an auxiliary unit of the *gmina* that does not have the status of local government unit and legal personality. The *sołectwo* has its own elected bodies: village meeting, village leader, village council. The *sołectwo* are established, transformed and liquidated independently by the *gmina*. The *sołectwo* operate in the area of rural *gminas* and rural-urban *gminas*. By contrast, in the area of cities, auxiliary units are usually entitled ‘districts’ (*dzielnica*).

For this purpose, the residents of the *sołectwo* must convene a village meeting at which such a request is adopted, including the description of an objective on which the financial resources from the municipality budget are to be spent (construction of a playground, repairs, construction of pavements, equipping of a voluntary fire brigade etc). As a general rule, the village meeting is convened by the village leader (*sołtys*) on his/her own initiative, and also on at the request of a certain numbers of residents entitled to attend the meeting (usually about 10 per cent).⁸⁵

The request can be made on the initiative of the village leader, village council or at least 15 adult *sołectwo* residents. Then the request is put to the vote of the village meeting. Voting procedures are determined by the statutes of each *sołectwo*.

The *gmina* council while adopting the municipality budget may refuse the *sołectwo* request when it considers that the tasks which the *sołectwo* is planning to implement do not meet the conditions determined in the act.

The following conditions should be met:

- the arrangements fall within the scope of the *gmina*'s own tasks;
- the arrangements comply with the *gmina*'s development strategy;
- the arrangements contribute to the improvement of residents living conditions.

If the following conditions are met the *gmina* council shall adopt the resolution on the inclusion of the financial arrangements from the 'Village fund' resources contribute to the *gmina*'s budget.

The tasks from the 'Village fund' resources are implemented as described in the request. The 'Village fund' is a part of the *gmina*'s budget for which implementation the mayor is responsible.

The role of village leader (*sołtys*) and residents is not limited to adopting and submitting requests. It involves:

- controlling the implementation term and the arrangements quality;
- participation in the arrangements implementation if it was decided during the village meeting. It may be their work or contribution in-kind.

Residents have the right to ask the mayor about the implementation term. This is guaranteed by the Polish Constitution, in Article 61. The mayor must respond within 14 days.

⁸⁵ These issues are regulated in the *sołectwo* statute. The statute of the *sołectwo* is adopted by the *gmina* council. Each *gmina* defines the text of the statute for all *sołectwos* that have been established on its territory. Therefore, the content of the statutes of various *sołectwos* may differ from each other.

Assessment of the Practice

The aim of the Act on the Village Fund was to ensure opportunities for the village residents to decide independently and jointly their environment and life quality.

The *sołectwo* may spend – in accordance with their needs – the financial resources but the residents must show initiative and cooperate with each other. The decision is made by the village meeting. It must be held democratically and lawfully. Such a possibility mobilizes leaders or groups of residents who not only initiate concrete actions but persuade others to implement them as well.

The data show large dynamics in the use of this instrument of public participation. In 2009 the number of *gminas* in which the Village fund was separated amounted to 1178, then, it increased steadily to reach the number of 1596 municipalities in 2018 where the authorities allow the village residents to take over a part of responsibility for the village development. The number of municipalities where the Village fund was established amounted in per cent: in 2009-2013 – 55 per cent, in 2015 – 65 per cent, in 2016 – 68 per cent, in 2017 - 71,3 per cent. In 2018 the number of *gminas* in Poland is 2478, the number of municipalities with (rural and urban-rural) *sołectwo* is 2174, and the number of *sołectwo* - 40 725. The amount of the return of a part of expenditures executed within the framework of the Village fund from the state budget increased steadily, in 2011 the return amounted to approx. PLN⁸⁶ 44 million, but in 2018 - PLN 124 million.

It was 10 years ago that this participation instrument of village residents was launched. This may enable the assessment of ‘Village fund’ function and the collection of a catalogue of good practices as well as the indication of possible weaknesses which should be eliminated. Certainly, the ‘Village fund’ will be continued by rural and urban-rural *gminas*, also because of the financial bonus from the government budget. The second factor will certainly be the desire to maintain the image of a ‘residents-friendly commune’, i.e. one that leaves part of the decisions directly to residents.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Bednarska-Olejniczak D and Olejniczak J, ‘Participatory Budgeting in Poland in 2013-2018 – Six Years of Experiences and Directions of Changes’ in Nelson Dias (ed), *Hope for Democracy – 30 Years of Participatory Budgeting Worldwide* (Epopeia Records Oficina 2018)

Jacobsson K and Korolczuk E (eds), *Civil Society Revisited: Lessons from Poland* (Berghahn Books 2017)

⁸⁶ 1 PLN (Polish zloty) is 0.23 Euro.

Mirska A, 'Village fund' (*Encyclopedia of Public Administration*, 2019)
<http://encyklopediaap.uw.edu.pl/index.php/Fundusz_so%C5%82ecki/en>

Strzelecki A, 'The Development of Participation Budget in the Civic Society of Kujawsko-Pomorskie Voivodship' (2018) 5 *Law and Administration in Post-Soviet Europe* 52
<<https://doi.org/10.2478/lape-2018-0006>>

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